

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP), WP3 - FAIRyMAGs - Optimising Metagenomics Assembled Genomes building: workflow finalisation, training material development, real data evaluation and resource allocation tool creation

M3.2 Recovered MAGs for selection of 3 real-world datasets

Tier: Science

Priority Area: Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP)

Executive Summary

This milestone presents the recovered metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) from selected real-world datasets using the workflows created by the FAIRyMAGs project. In collaboration with the project partners, four real-world datasets were chosen to represent a diverse range of challenges for MAGs generation. Although the milestone initially required only three datasets, the scope was expanded to four due to their scientific relevance and representative use cases.

The selected datasets include samples from the (i) bee gut microbiome¹ (ENA Project ID: PRJNA977416), (ii) aeromicrobiome (collected from clouds and aerosols at an altitude of 1,465 m on the Puy de Dôme mountain in France²; ENA Project ID: PRJEB54740), (iii) termite head microbiome (unpublished), and (iv) macroalgal microbiome³ (ENA Project ID: PRJNA915238).

The workflows developed within the FAIRyMAGs project were applied to all use cases. These included **short-read quality control**, **host-read removal**, and the main **metagenome-assembled genome (MAG) generation** workflows.

This milestone focuses on the quality (completeness and contamination) and the number of recovered MAGs. An expert evaluation in a biological context will be executed in D3.2 (*Assessed MAGs and their quality for the 3 selected real-world datasets*).

Author List

Node	Institution	Name, surname	ORCID
DE-G... ▾	Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Freiburg	Paul, Zierrep	0000-0003-2 982-388X
FR-Fr... ▾	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE (CNRS)	Bérénice, Batut	0000-0001-9 852-1987
IT-Italy ▾	University of Bari "Aldo Moro"	Giuseppe, Defazio	0000-0002-9 356-5224
DE-G... ▾	Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Freiburg	Mina, Ansari	0000-0002-3 602-7884

Reviewers

Node	Institution* (please choose from the list above)	Name, surname	ORCID
DE-Ge... ▾	Research Center Jülich GmbH, Jülich	Sebastian, Beier	0000-0002- 2177-8781
FR-Fra... ▾	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE (CNRS)	Anne-Françoise, ADAM-BLONDON	0000-0002- 3412-9086

Abbreviations and Acronyms

MAGs	metagenome-assembled genomes
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
IWC	Intergalactic Workflow Commission

Workflow Execution

For all use cases, the Galaxy workflows developed in D3.1 (*Workflow available on UseGalaxy Europe and UseGalaxy France servers as well as published on IWC and WorkflowHub*) for [short-read quality control](#) and [host-read removal](#), and the [main metagenome-assembled genome \(MAG\) generation workflow](#) were executed. The default parameters of the workflows were used except for some modifications depending on the use case. For all use cases, the human reference genome hg38 (GRCh38) was used for the removal of potential human contamination. For the bee microbiome use case, the bee reference genome (*A. mellifera* genome: apiMel3.1 NCBI GCF_003254395.2) was also used to remove host contamination.

For the aeromicrobiome use case, the assembly tool metaSPAdes⁴ was used instead of MEGAHIT⁵ since benchmark studies⁶ have shown that metaSPAdes performs better than MEGAHIT on metagenomes where low community complexity is expected, such as airborne metagenomics⁷. Both assemblers are integrated into the main metagenome-assembled genome (MAG) generation workflow, allowing users to seamlessly switch between them depending on project requirements.

Almost all workflows were successfully executed. The exception was for the aeromicrobiome use case, where one job exceeded the available memory and could not be run on the public resources provided by usegalaxy.eu. In addition, not all binning tools completed successfully for every dataset, which is consistent with known limitations of binning software when applied to small or highly fragmented assemblies.

To mitigate technical issues during assembly and/or binning, a **fallback workflow** was developed. This workflow enables MAG recovery even when individual assembly or binning jobs fail, representing a practical compromise between computational constraints and overall MAG recovery. Implementing such a dynamic recovery workflow would be challenging in workflow managers such as Nextflow or Snakemake, as these frameworks are designed around strictly defined execution graphs and typically do not support conditional continuation based on partial tool failures without substantial custom logic or manual intervention.

The main workflow was updated from v0.3 to v0.4 to generate standardized, combined tabular outputs for MAG annotation, taxonomic assignment, and genome quality. These outputs are compatible with a tool currently in development that produces high-quality, study-wide figures of MAG statistics (<https://github.com/SantaMcCloud/MAGs-visualization>). To ensure that combined tables were available for all use cases, an adapted version of the workflow that only runs the table generation tools was applied across all datasets. This highlights the flexibility provided by using the Galaxy workflow manager.

Recovered MAGs

The workflows successfully recovered MAGs for all four use cases, although the number and quality of the recovered MAGs varied significantly between use cases. This is expected since the use cases differ markedly in sample complexity, community composition, and sequencing depth, all of which strongly influence assembly contiguity, binning performance, and ultimately MAG recovery.

The results of the MAGs workflows for each use case are available as public Galaxy histories. The final dereplicated MAGs are tagged as `Dereplicated-Bins`.

Use case	Public History
Bee microbiome	Recovered MAGs: https://usegalaxy.eu/u/paulzierep/h/prjna977416-bee-use-case-1-1 Result tables: https://usegalaxy.eu/u/santinof/h/annotation-wf-bee-use-case
Aeromicrobiome	Recovered MAGs with main workflow: https://usegalaxy.eu/u/paulzierep/h/cloud-use-case-1-1 Recovered MAGs with recovery workflow: https://usegalaxy.eu/u/paulzierep/h/binning-fallback-1 Result tables: https://usegalaxy.eu/u/santinof/h/annotation-wf-cloud-use-case
Termite head microbiome	Recovered MAGs: https://usegalaxy.eu/u/mina24/h/head-samples-1 Result tables: https://usegalaxy.eu/u/santinof/h/annotation-wf-termite-use-case
Macroalgal microbiome	Recovered MAGs: https://usegalaxy.eu/u/gdefazio/h/upload-prjna915238 Result tables: https://usegalaxy.eu/u/santinof/h/annotation-wf-marine-use-case

Figure 1 shows the recovered MAGs for different thresholds of completeness and contamination for all use cases.

Figure 1. Effect of contamination and completeness thresholds on MAG recovery across use cases. Horizontal stacked bar plots show the number of dereplicated representatives of metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) recovered from the four environments (Bee, Air, Termite, and Marine), grouped by completeness thresholds. Panel (A) includes MAGs with contamination <5%, and panel (B) includes MAGs with contamination <10%. The numbers at the end of each bar indicate total dereplicated MAG counts.

The aeromicrobiome dataset yielded the fewest MAGs, underscoring the substantial challenges associated with DNA extraction and biomass recovery from this environment; as a result, only a single high-quality MAG could be reconstructed. In contrast, the termite and bee microbiome use cases produced a higher number of MAGs, likely reflecting more favorable sampling and extraction conditions as well as less complex and more host-associated microbial communities, which facilitate genome reconstruction. The marine use case resulted in the largest number of recovered MAGs, consistent with good sampling conditions and sequencing depth, but also reflecting the vast diversity and heterogeneity of marine microbial communities, which provide many recoverable genomes despite increased environmental complexity.

Exemplary MAGs from the Bee Microbiome Use Case

The main metagenome-assembled genome (MAG) generation workflow not only produces MAGs and reports quality metrics, but also performs species-level dereplication, assigns taxonomy, estimates sample-specific abundances, and annotates genes within each genome. Figure 2 summarizes the metrics generated for the bee use case. Species-level clusters represent MAGs for which similar genomes were recovered across multiple samples, providing strong evidence of genome quality. Of the 161 recovered MAGs, 38 species-level representatives could be dereplicated. Overall, high completeness and low contamination, as determined by CheckM2⁸, support the high quality of the MAGs. Many MAGs were classified at the phylum level as Pseudomonadota (formerly Proteobacteria) and Bacillota (formerly Firmicutes),

consistent with the core bee gut microbiome⁹. A detailed analysis of the biological context for each use case will be presented in D3.2 (*Assessed MAGs and their quality for the three selected real-world datasets*).

Figure 2. Top 30 species-level clustered MAGs from the Bee use case. Bars indicate the number of MAGs that are $\geq 95\%$ similar to the representative MAG selected as the workflow output. Taxonomic assignments at the phylum and genus levels are shown alongside each bar. MAG quality metrics, including completeness, contamination, genome size, GC content, and the number of annotated genes (CDS), are displayed in the accompanying heatmap.

Dissemination Plans

The recovered MAGs will be published alongside the preprint planned in Milestone M3.6 (*Preprint submitted on BioRxiv*). While it remains to be determined whether the MAGs can be deposited in ENA as a third-party submission, this will be pursued if feasible. In any case, the MAGs will be deposited in a public archive together with the annotation and quality statistics.

The fallback MAGs recovery workflow will be published to IWC and then will be available on WorkflowHub.

Citations

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